

Distributed Application of the Traffic Scheduling Technique for Smart Grid Advanced Metering Applications Using Multi-Gate Mesh Networks

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Abstract—In this paper, we present a multi-gate mesh network architecture that has been developed to ensure high performance and reliability under emergency conditions when a system expects to receive power outage notifications and exchanges. In order to handle the metering traffic, we introduce a back-pressure based scheduling algorithm, which takes into account both the hop-count, as well as the queue length of each mesh node. We first present the objective function of the scheduling algorithm in a centralized manner. We then present a practical implementation of the packet-scheduling scheme. The simulation results indicate that, under the context of the multi-gateway network, our novel packet-scheduling scheme can indeed significantly improve the network's reliability, self-healing, throughput and delay performance.

Keywords- smart grid; back-pressure; multi-gate; mesh network

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important issues in Smart Grid (as defined in the Energy Independence and Security Act of 2007), is to provide a reliable and secure two-way end-to-end communications system for the Advanced Metering Infrastructure (AMI). The AMI system aims at providing consumers with knowledge of their energy usage and the capability of monitoring and controlling the electrical system components. While networking technologies and systems have been greatly enhanced, the smart grid faces challenges in terms of reliability and security in both wired and wireless communication environments. For instance, smart home appliances represent a major part of the Smart Grid vision of improving energy efficiency and they have to communicate with entities and players in other Smart Grid domains via home area and neighborhood area networks. For inter-operable networks, the appropriate use of wired and wireless technologies has been the main focus for smart grid last mile communication networks.

One example is Power Line Communication (PLC) [1]–[3], which is receiving considerable attention for home area networking applications. At the same time, Wireless LAN (WLAN) techniques, such as the IEEE 802.11 family standards [4] with their maturity and cost effectiveness, have been extensively deployed for wireless access and home entertainment. However, to provide a large coverage area for AMI in residential areas, multi-hop communication is vastly favored

over long-range single-hop links. Indeed, the benefit of multi-hop transmissions is that of combating the rapid decay of the received electromagnetic signal strength, as the communication distance increases. Although there has been a tremendous advancement in mesh networking from the architectural point of view, the AMI network should be designed to ensure a high degree of reliability, self-configuration, and self-healing. Meeting these requirements depends not only on the selection of a mesh routing protocol, Medium Access Control (MAC) protocols, and physical (PHY) layer, but also on the nature of the traffic at its application layer. For example, the time-varying traffic generated under emergency situations poses a significant challenge in ensuring the reliability of the smart grid network. In particular, outage management is one example where a system expects to receive power outage notifications and an exchange of information among all the meters. This situation tends to increase traffic load, resulting in severe network congestion. Furthermore, in a multi-hop mesh network, a meter which represents a mesh node should not only transmit its own generated packets, but also those received from neighboring meters.

In the case of a conventional neighborhood area network, a residential area is normally divided into separate regions where meters (i.e., mesh nodes) in each region communicate with the AMI headend through their local gateway point. Under such conditions, meters closer to the local gateway (i.e., last hop nodes) are expected to experience more severe congestion than those further away. This could create a bottleneck, especially under outage conditions. In order to allow collective participation in the routing, it is advantageous to combine all the sub-networks into a larger network with multiple gateways where meters can access any of the gateways based on local traffic activity.

This strategy would require every meter to possess a separate route to each of the gateways. Assuming that such a routing requirement can be accomplished by designing an appropriate routing protocol, a major step would be to balance the traffic load amongst the gateways. To tackle this important issue we consider a back-pressure based algorithm in the context of the multi-gate network. The original concept of the back-pressure algorithm for a multi-hop network was first intro

Fig. 1: An example of a multiple-path network structure consisting of G gateways (G_1, G_2, \dots, G_G).

duced in [5]. Since then, this algorithm has been applied to many areas of wired/wireless communication systems [6]–[8].

However, the delay performance of the original back-pressure algorithm [5] may become uncontrollable for the following two reasons. Firstly, given F classes of flows in the entire ad-hoc network, which are distinguished by destination, F queues remain at each mesh node, although only one queue is served at a time. Secondly, due to a lack of contribution from the hop-count to the objective function, it is quite possible that the original back-pressure algorithm in [5] may route some packets through a much longer way rather than the shortest path to the necessary destination.

Against this background, *our first contribution is to propose a novel hop-count based single-class back pressure scheduling algorithm, which can significantly reduce the delay compared with the original back pressure algorithm [5].* Admittedly, the authors of [9] have put forward a novel objective function for the centralized algorithm, which jointly takes into account the hop-count as well as the data waiting in the buffer for each node's concern. However, due to the instinct of single-destination, it doesn't change the multi-class queuing data structure maintained at each node, where a separate queue is maintained for every class of packets. Since the destination of each new packet injected into the mesh network has been determined and could be any of the nodes constituting the network, the hop counts to all potential destinations need to be obtained from time to time. This definitely adds to the traffic load, as well as the complexity of calculating the objective function, hence increasing the delay of the proposed algorithm.

As opposed to previous open sources [5]–[9], *our second contribution is to embed our novel scheduling algorithm into a multi-gateway network structure, where the destination of any packet injected is not fixed beforehand.* In other words, the final destination may vary as the packet passes through each relay-node and cannot be determined until it reaches the final destination. Given this flexibility, the processing delay is

significantly reduced as only one queue needs to be maintained at each node.

The scheduling solutions presented by all the above mentioned back-pressure based algorithms, i.e. [5], [9], are achieved by optimizing the centralized objective functions via exhaustively searching all possible scheduling solutions. These centralized algorithms require too much time and complexity to implement in the context of ad-hoc wireless communication. Thus, a large variety of distributed algorithms, such as those of [11]–[13], were proposed to apply the objective functions featuring the centralized algorithms. *Our third contribution is to derive the distributed objective function from the centralized objective function used by our novel scheduling algorithm, so that it can be used for practical implementation.* Finally, *our fourth contribution is providing the simulation results achieved by our novel distributed algorithm, in terms of both the throughput and the delay performance.*

The organization of the paper is as follows. In Section II the multi-gate mesh network architecture is presented. In Section III, the novel multi-gateway hop-count and queue-length based back-pressure algorithm is proposed. In Section IV-A, the objective function of the distributed implementation method is derived from the objective function employed by the proposed novel centralized algorithm. Other aspects of the implementation of the proposed algorithm are also discussed in Section IV-B. In Section V, the simulation results, using a proactive tree-based routing, are presented followed by the conclusion and final remarks, which are presented in Section VI.

II. MULTI-GATE ROUTING NETWORK ARCHITECTURE

A neighborhood area network may consist of multiple mesh sub-networks where mesh nodes representing meters in each sub-network can only access the local gateway. Each gateway, which is also referred to as the Data Aggregation Point (DAP) by the smart grid community is connected to the master gateway (headend) via a wired or wireless link.

Due to the variable nature of the traffic, some gateways may suffer from more congestion than others. Under such conditions, nodes belonging to neighboring sub-networks cannot participate in the routing to reduce the traffic load. In order to allow collective participation in the routing, it would be advantageous to combine all the sub-networks into a larger network with multiple gateways (DAPs) where all the meters can access any of the gateways, as shown in Fig. 1. This arrangement is expected to enhance the self-healing and self-organization abilities of the network if some of the gateways and nodes become non-operational or new nodes are added to expand the network. Designing such a network would require developing a flexible multi-gate routing protocol so that each node (meter) can have a separate path to the gateways: G_1, G_2, \dots, G_G . We use symbol \mathbb{G} to denote the set containing all the gateways in the entire investigated mesh network. In addition to the G gateways, there are N mesh nodes scattered in the local wireless network. The n th node among them can be denoted as

\mathbb{N}_n . $\hat{H}(\mathbb{N}_n)$ stands for the number of hop counts from node N_n to the nearest gateway, for any $n \in [1, N]$. More specifically, $\hat{H}(\mathbb{N}_n)$ can be defined as

$$\hat{H}(\mathbb{N}_n) = \min_{\dot{G} \in \dot{G}} H(\mathbb{N}_n \rightarrow \dot{G}), \quad (1)$$

where $H(\mathbb{N}_n \rightarrow \dot{G})$ stands for the number of hop counts associated with the shortest path from node N_n to gateway \dot{G} .

As the maximum number of hops of a loop-free route is limited by a fixed number H , the set containing all the N mesh nodes, i.e. \mathbb{N} , can be divided into H subsets according to the value of $\hat{H}(\mathbb{N}_n)$. More specifically, the set \mathbb{N}_h comprises all the N_h nodes that are h hops away from the nearest gateways, when $h = 1, 2, \dots, H$. For the sake of convenience, we denote the N_h nodes in \mathbb{N}_h uniquely by $N_{h,1}, N_{h,2}, \dots, N_{h,N_h}$. Additionally, the queue length of the packets inside the buffer of node $N_{h,i}$, with $h = 1, 2, \dots, H$ and $i = 1, 2, \dots$, is denoted as $Q(\mathbb{N}_{h,i})$.

The routing matrix is denoted as \mathbf{R} , having elements from the set $\{+1, -1, 0\}$, representing all the one-hop links in the wireless mesh network. The N rows of matrix \mathbf{R} correspond to the N mesh nodes, and its L columns correspond to all the L single-hop single-direction links. The j th column of \mathbf{R} comprising of N elements, describes the two nodes connected to link L_j . More specifically, the element of the row corresponding to the transmitter of link L_j is set to $+1$, and that corresponding to the receiver is assigned to -1 . All other $(N-2)$ elements in the j th column are set to zero.

An $(L \times 1)$ -element binary vector \mathbf{s} can be used to represent a sample activation vector. If the i th element of \mathbf{s} is equivalent to one, $\text{Link } L_i$ should be activated. Conversely, if the i th element of \mathbf{s} is equivalent to zero, $\text{Link } L_i$ is not supposed to be activated. The elements values of \mathbf{s} are determined so that they comply with the selected interference model. That is, if all the links indicated by indexes of the non-zero elements of \mathbf{s} are activated during the same time slot, no inter-link interference will occur. Given a certain interference model, there will be more than one solution \mathbf{s} satisfying the condition given by the model to guarantee interference free simultaneous transmission. For brevity, all the possible solutions complying a certain interference model are collectively included in set \mathbb{S} . Therefore, the vector-elements in \mathbb{S} are recorded as $\mathbf{s}_1, \mathbf{s}_2, \dots, \mathbf{s}_{|\mathbb{S}|}$, where $|\mathbb{S}|$ is the cardinality of \mathbb{S} the number of vectors in \mathbb{S} . $\mathbf{e} \in \mathbb{S}$ denotes the activation vector that is ultimately selected out among all the vectors in \mathbb{S} for the next time slot, based on the objective function provided by the scheduling algorithm.

III. SCHEDULING ALGORITHM OF MESH NODES

We assume that the hop-count of a node to the nearest gateway is known. For an arbitrary node $N_{h,i} \in \mathbb{N}_h$, any of its neighbors is included in one of the sets \mathbb{N}_{h-1} , \mathbb{N}_h and \mathbb{N}_{h+1} . Hence, in order to reduce the delay of forwarding the data packets initiated at the node $N_{h,i}$ to any of the G gateways, its neighboring nodes belonging to \mathbb{N}_{h-1} have the privilege over the nodes from sets \mathbb{N}_h and \mathbb{N}_{h+1} as the next hop.

Apart from the delay, maximizing the throughput of the network is another objective to be taken into account by the scheduling algorithm. In order to accommodate a larger arrival rate initiated at each node, the queue length of each node should be reduced rather than increased with time and a balance of the queue length among all nodes should be observed with time passing. Hence, the neighboring nodes of the transmitter node $N_{h,i}$, having a shorter queue size, should enjoy the privilege of being a receiver. Based on the above discussion the centralized scheduling algorithm is quantified as

$$\mathbf{e} = \arg \max_{\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{S}} \{ \mathbf{d}^T \bar{\mathbf{D}} \mathbf{s} \}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{s} is an arbitrary combination of interference-free links that can be simultaneously activated. In (2), the set \mathbb{S} contains all the available combinations of interference-free links that can be simultaneously activated in the entire mesh network. Additionally, the $(L \times 1)$ -element vector \mathbf{d} and the $(L \times L)$ -element matrix $\bar{\mathbf{D}}$ in (2) represent the difference in queue length and hop-count between the transmitters and their respective receivers associated with the L single-hop direct links. Given the transmitting node of link L_i denoted as $T(L_i)$ and its receiver node as $R(L_i)$, the i th element of \mathbf{d} is defined as $d_i = Q[T(L_i)] - Q[R(L_i)]$, where $Q(\mathbb{N}_n)$ stands for the number of packets waiting to be transmitted in the buffer of node N_n , for any $n \in [1, N]$.

In (2), the $(L \times L)$ -element diagonal matrix $\bar{\mathbf{D}}$ can be further formulated as: $\bar{\mathbf{D}} = (\mathbf{D} + \mu)\nu$, where \mathbf{D} is a diagonal matrix with its i th diagonal element $D_i \in \{+1, 0, -1\}$, for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, L$. The element D_i indicates the hop-count difference between the transmitter and receiver of link L_i , and is defined as: $D_i = \hat{H}[T(L_i)] - \hat{H}[R(L_i)]$, where the implication of $\hat{H}[T(L_i)]$ has been defined in (1). Given $T(L_i) \in \mathbb{N}_h$, the value of D_i can only fall into one of the following three categories: $D_i = +1$ if $R(L_i) \in \mathbb{N}_{h-1}$, $D_i = 0$ if $R(L_i) \in \mathbb{N}_h$ and $D_i = -1$ if $R(L_i) \in \mathbb{N}_{h+1}$. In order to make the parameters positive regardless of the scenarios, so that it can be used to calculate the objective function in (2), two adjustable parameters μ and ν are introduced. Hence, three parameters, namely α , β and γ are sufficient to quantify all the non-zero elements in $\bar{\mathbf{D}}$. More exactly, $\alpha = (+1 + \mu)\nu$, $\beta = (0 + \mu)\nu$ and $\gamma = (-1 + \mu)\nu$.

IV. DISTRIBUTED IMPLEMENTATION

Before revealing the distributed approach of applying the centralized algorithm featured by the objective function (2) of Section III, the definition of Single Node Metric (SNM) and Single Link Metric (SLM) will be presented. The SNM is the product of the queue length of a certain node, multiplied by its hop count to the nearest gateway. More quantitatively, given a node $N_i \in \mathbb{N}$ for all $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, the SNM $W(N_i)$ can be defined as $W(N_i) = Q(N_i)\hat{H}(N_i)$, where $\hat{H}(N_i)$ has been defined in (1). On the other hand, SLM represents the merit of a single-hop direct link. The value of SLM associated with a link roughly stands for the SNM-value difference between the transmitter and the receiver. More quantitatively, for a given link L_i , the SLM $W(L_i)$ of it can be defined as $W(L_i) =$

$d(L_i)\bar{D}(L_i)$, where the scalar $d(L_i)$ quantifies the queue-length difference between the transmitter $T(L_i)$ and the receiver $R(L_i)$. More exactly, we have $\bar{D}(L_i) = [\hat{H}[T(L_i)] - \hat{H}[R(L_i)] + \mu]v$, where μ and v are both parameters. It may be worth mentioning that $d_i = d(L_i)$ is the i th element of the $(L \times 1)$ -element vector \mathbf{d} and $\bar{D}_i = \bar{D}(L_i)$ is the i th diagonal element of the $(L \times L)$ -element matrix \mathbf{D} , which constitute parts of the objective function in (2) characterizing the centralized scheduling algorithm described in Section III.

A. Objective Function used by Distributed Implementation

For a G -gateway system, let us assume that a transmitting node $N_{h,t}$ has M neighbors $B_1(N_{h,t}), B_2(N_{h,t}), \dots, B_M(N_{h,t})$. The objective function of the centralized algorithm, as quantified by (2) can be alternatively interpreted using the term SLM as:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{e}(\mathbb{L}) &= \arg \max_{\mathbf{s}(\mathbb{L}) \subset \mathbb{S}(\mathbb{L})} \left\{ \sum_{L_i \in \mathbf{s}(\mathbb{L})} [\text{SLM}(L_i)] \right\} \\ &= \arg \max_{\mathbf{s}(\mathbb{L}) \subset \mathbb{S}(\mathbb{L})} \left\{ \sum_{L_i \in \mathbf{s}(\mathbb{L})} [W(L_i)] \right\} \\ &= \arg \max_{\mathbf{s}(\mathbb{L}) \subset \mathbb{S}(\mathbb{L})} \left\{ \sum_{L_i \in \mathbf{s}(\mathbb{L})} [(Q[T(L_i)] - Q[R(L_i)]) \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. (\hat{H}[T(L_i)] - \hat{H}[R(L_i)] + \mu)v] \right\}, \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{e}(\mathbb{L})$ is the set of links that are finally activated during the next time slot, in a centralized algorithm and obviously $\mathbf{e}(\mathbb{L}) \subset \mathbb{L}$, i.e. $\mathbf{e}(\mathbb{L})$ is a subset of \mathbb{L} . Moreover $\mathbf{s}(\mathbb{L})$ is an arbitrary set of links that could be simultaneously activated without interference. Additionally, $\mathbb{S}(\mathbb{L})$ is a second-level set containing all the sets of mutually interference-free links that could be activated simultaneously. Apparently, $\mathbf{e}(\mathbb{L}) \subset \mathbb{S}(\mathbb{L})$ is a particular subset of $\mathbb{S}(\mathbb{L})$ that can maximize the objective function displayed in (3).

In the distributed counterpart, for a given node $N_{h,t}$, the concern is to select a single destination $R(N_{h,t})$ among all its neighbors $B_1(N_{h,t}), B_2(N_{h,t}), \dots, B_M(N_{h,t})$ as the next hop. Naturally, the given node $N_{h,t}$ constitutes a transmitting node of a certain link L_i , and the receiver node should be selected from its neighbor-set $\mathbb{B}(N_{h,t})$ based on an objective function. Due to a lack of SNM knowledge of the nodes, other than opting for its neighbors in the distributed regime, the system is unable to jointly choose the transmitters and receivers of all the links to be simultaneously activated during the next time slot, as implied by the objective function of the centralized algorithm in (3). Instead, each link with a fixed transmitter will choose its receiver independently in the distributed regime. As long as a receiver node $R(N_{h,t})$ is selected from the neighbors of $N_{h,t}$, a link transmitting one packet from $N_{h,t}$ to $R(N_{h,t})$ will be activated. More specifically, the next hop of a certain link L_i starting from $T(L_i)$ is selected as:

$$\begin{aligned} R(T(L_i)) &= \arg \max_{R(L_i) \in \mathbb{B}(T(L_i))} \left\{ (Q[T(L_i)] - Q[R(L_i)]) \times \right. \\ &\quad \left. (\hat{H}[T(L_i)] - \hat{H}[R(L_i)] + \mu)v \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

As can be observed from the objective function of the distributed application in (4), as opposite to the objective

function of the centralized algorithm in (3), there is no element of other links $L_j \neq L_i$ presented in the objective function of choosing the receiver of a certain link L_i .

Since both the value of $Q[T(L_i)]$ and $\hat{H}[T(L_i)]$ makes no difference for different node $R(L_i) \in \mathbb{B}(T(L_i))$, the identical part related to the transmitting node in (4) can be omitted only when the receiver node is concerned. Then (4) can be simplified as:

$$\begin{aligned} R(T(L_i)) &= \arg \min_{R(L_i) \in \mathbb{B}(T(L_i))} \left\{ Q[R(L_i)] (\hat{H}[R(L_i)] + \mu)v \right\} \\ &= \arg \min_{R(L_i) \in \mathbb{B}(T(L_i))} \left\{ Q[R(L_i)] \hat{H}[R(L_i)] \right\}. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Substituting $T(L_i)$ for $N_{h,t}$ and $R(L_i)$ for \hat{N} , (5) is finalized as

$$R(N_{h,t}) = \min_{\hat{N} \in \mathbb{B}(N_{h,t})} \left\{ \hat{H}[\hat{N}] \cdot Q[\hat{N}] \right\}, \quad (6)$$

which constitutes the objective function for selecting the receiver $R(N_{h,t})$ for a given node $N_{h,t}$, among all its neighbor-set $\mathbb{B}(N_{h,t})$. As can be seen by the objective function of (6), the distributed algorithm can only determine the next hop for a given transmitting node. When a certain node is chosen by several transmitting nodes as the next hop, the distributed manner has no way of predicting or scheduling these potential transmitting nodes. Conversely, according to the centralized algorithm given in Section III, the overall optimal arrangement will not allow one receiving node to have two transmitting nodes simultaneously. More particularly, for example, if a node has the smallest SNM value among the neighboring nodes of two nodes, the node having the higher SNM value will be determined as the node to transmit a packet to the receiving node during the next time slot.

B. Identify the Headings

Based on the network structure depicted in Fig. 1 and the multi-path requirement of our packet-scheduling scheme, it would be essential to design a flexible multi-gate routing protocol so that meters can have the option to select the best path to one of the gateways. Although there are varieties of mesh routing protocols that can be used for our network, we have selected a tree-based routing protocol. It is based on the Hybrid Wireless Mesh Protocol (HWMP), which is a default routing protocol for the IEEE 802.11s [4]. An important feature of the IEEE 802.11s is that it supports frame forwarding and path selection at layer 2 instead of layer 3 (network layer). However, due to the static nature of the mesh network, we only consider the proactive part of this hybrid protocol by extending it for our multi-gate network according to the network configuration shown in Fig. 1.

To incorporate a multiple routing according to the network structure shown in Fig. 1, each gateway (G_1, G_2, \dots, G_G) as the root of a tree periodically broadcasts root announcements to set up its tree. We use a randomization technique to avoid collision of root enhancement messages. The MAC addresses of G_1, G_2, \dots, G_G are employed as the unique identifications that correspond to the root announcements from the routing trees. In contrast to single gateway, a node in a multi-gate topology has

Fig. 2: Performance evaluation of the three-gateway network with and without using back-pressure algorithm.

Fig. 4: The throughput performance of the back-pressure scheme with three gateways (G_1 , G_2 and G_3), 36 flows and a beacon interval of 0.2.

Fig. 3: The throughput performance of the best-path scheme with three gateways (G_1 , G_2 and G_3), 36 flows and a beacon interval of 0.2 second.

Fig. 5: Average end-to-end delay of the three-gateway network with and without using back-pressure algorithm..

multiple entries in its tree-table representing a separate path to each gateway [14]. For example, one entry represents a tree with G_1 as its root, which also includes its parent information, as well as the status of the tree (i.e., whether it is active or not). When a mesh node (meter) receives a root announcement, it will check its tree-table to see if there is a tree with the same root announcement. If not, the meter will generate a new tree in its table by using the information from the received root announcement message, where gateway and parent information, as well the tree-status are created and maintained. If yes, the node will upgrade the existing tree with the same gateway if newer or better path information is contained in the received announcement message. Otherwise, it will discard this announcement message. Meanwhile, a mesh node (meter) will set up a path to the new gateway in its route table if there is no route available to this gateway. It should be noted that the main objective is for every mesh node (meter) to systematically select the most suitable gateway through which the packets will be routed to the master gateway (headend). With respect to the implementation of the proposed back-pressure scheme, the main objective would be the selection of the next hop based on the SNM value. Therefore, in obtaining the SNM value, only the parent nodes may be used in the calculation. This is consis-

tent with the centralized algorithm, as the parents nodes are assigned with a higher metric \hat{D} value, as detailed in Section III.

According to (6) in the proposed back-pressure scheme, the queue-length and hop-count need to be calculated by a transmitting node, before scheduling its packet to the next hop's node. To accomplish this, we consider using beacon frames, which are primarily used by a node to update its neighbors about its current route to the destination. For example, when a node receives a beacon frame (or an association request) from its neighboring mesh node, it creates (or updates) a neighbor list according to the information in the beacon frame. The period of sending a beacon frame should depend on the traffic model. At a high packet rate, a faster update for calculating (6) may be needed and this would be at the expense of higher overhead. It is important to emphasize that the proposed back-pressure scheme relies on the multi-path routing described earlier. Every node should possess an active path to all the gateways (or at least a few neighboring gateways for a large network). When a mesh node (meter) receives a packet from its upper layer (self generated packet) or a neighboring node (relayed packet), it checks its neighbor list and compares the corresponding metrics.

As the parent list is updated by a root announcement process, the neighbors' list is updated and maintained through the beacon frames. In our implementation, the second smallest value in (6) will be selected from the same list to represent the next hop node in the case of link failure. In this back-pressure scheme the route error message is blocked in order to reduce the overhead in the network. For instance, when a link from node A to node B is broken due to consecutive packet losses, node A will re-schedule all the packets from its data queue by selecting the second best neighbor as its next hop destination. We should point out however, that since in this scheme the main objective is selection of the next hop, rather than the entire multi-hop path to the destination, there would be no need for on-demand routing.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

In our simulation model, a multi-gateway network is constructed that comprises three gateways G_1 , G_2 , and G_3 and 36 meters, which are uniformly distributed. In simulations the input data generated at a Variable Bit Rate (VBR), is encapsulated into fixed 512 bytes User Datagram Packet (UDP) packets. In the physical layer the IEEE 802.11b standard is used and the data-rate is 2 Mbps, while gateways are assumed to have an unlimited bit rate. The noise factor is 10.0 and the retransmission limit is 7. For the sake of comparison we also compare the performance of the combined multi-gate network operating with and without packet scheduling. In the absence of packet scheduling, the shortest path leading to the nearest gateway is selected. Fig. 2 shows the effective throughput versus input bit rate performance at the final destination point (headend).

In order to justify the throughput efficiency of the back-pressure scheme, traffic load distribution amongst the three gateways in the absence and presence of the back-pressure scheme are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. These results indicate that by directing the traffic towards gateways with less traffic, the back-pressure scheme is capable of effectively balancing the traffic load between gateways. Consequently, the overall throughput performance at the master gateway (headend) is enhanced, as shown in Fig. 4.

The next step in our evaluation is to compare the delay performance of the multi-gate scheme with and without packet scheduling. Fig. 5 shows their respective average end-to-end delay performances. As can be observed, the back-pressure scheme shows a significant improvement in delay performance as compared with the single best-path scheme.

From these results we can clearly observe that the flexibility of the back-pressure scheme combined with the multi-path feature of the multi-gate network structure can be effectively distributed amongst the gateways.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper we propose a novel multi-gateway network structure and, under this architecture, we propose a novel packet-scheduling algorithm aimed at providing reliable two-way communications from meters to the AMI headend, which can maintain a trade-off between maximizing the throughput and minimizing the average overall network delay. Ultimately, we derive our novel distributed objective function from the centralized algorithm and implement it with simulation. The simulation results further justify the ability of the novel scheduling algorithm in raising the network throughput and reducing the overall delay.

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